

Moso-Diez, M. (2019). VET and business strategies of manufacturing companies in Spain. In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.148-152) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641852>

VET and Business Strategies of Manufacturing Companies in Spain

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to analyse the business strategies of Spanish companies in terms of Vocational Education and Training (VET), identifying and studying the general characteristics of Spanish manufacturing companies and their differences based on human resources employed with professional training. This analysis will be developed quantitatively, within the framework of the Business Strategies Survey of SEPI Foundation, which is an annual panel survey, aimed at industrial manufacturing companies based in Spain. The survey referred to 2016-2017 will incorporate, for the first time, some items related to VET, being surveyed 1800 industrial companies. This analysis will be developed from a knowledge economy approach. The contribution of this research makes to the field lies in its novel comparative approach and in the quantitative scale of the sample. Nevertheless, the research has its limitations and that it is necessary to continue study in this significant scientific field.

Keywords

vocational education and training; business strategies; manufacturing industry; productivity; innovation

1 Introduction

As established by the Lisbon Strategy (2000) and the current Growth Strategy (2010), the key to competitiveness, inclusiveness and sustainability lies in the capacity to create knowledge societies. In this context, companies face the constant challenge of achieving a competitive advantage which requires them to reflect on how to do it and conditions the strategies they adopt to do so. Firms' strategies vary widely and evolve in line with shifts in markets, economies and society in general. So, which path to choose? Specialisation or diversification, expansion or concentration, differentiation or cost, innovation or improvement?

In all these decisions and strategies, one factor remains constant and universal: the knowledge the company has access to (Grant, 1996; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995; etc.) and, especially, the skills its employees possess (Leiponen, 2000; Murray and Steedman, 1998; etc.). The people who make up a firm are its driving force. It is they who reflect on, develop and implement the strategies selected. Aware of this, companies are increasingly putting mechanisms in place to discover what knowledge they need to achieve their strategic aims, whether or not they have it in-house and if they don't, how they can obtain it (e.g. through training, recruitment, outsourcing, and so on). In recent years, Europe-wide analysis has highlighted the importance of investing in vocational education and training (VET), revealing the positive impact it has on productivity and/or innovation as firms adapt to ever-greater digitisation, process automation and, in general, the incorporation of new technologies. It is relevant to note that empirical studies indicate that a positive of value creation (Jones, 2011; Wolter and Mühlemann, 2015; Cedefop, 2011; Mahlberg et al., 2009; Konings, 2008; Huerta et al., 2006; Zwick, 2006; Aragón-Sánchez, 2003; Alba-Ramirez, 1994), although the parameters of

analysis are diverse and heterogeneous and require further development, especially in the Spanish case.

In this highly demanding and competitive context, VET makes a key contribution to learning both because it delivers new cohorts of graduates of the formal VET system (aimed at young people and known as initial vocational education and training — IVET) and because it updates workers' knowledge throughout their professional lives through the VET for employment system (available both to those in work and those unemployed). While education's socio-economic importance has been studied extensively, VET has received limited attention and research has been disperse and fragmented. In the last decade, however, a new line of work has emerged that is making steady, albeit slow, progress. This is reflected in the Riga Conclusions, in which the EU has committed to enhancing the outcomes of VET (2015–2020) as regards the international competitiveness of the human capital emerging from VET programmes and achieving greater recognition for vocational qualifications. As a result, professional competencies and skills are now part of the European agenda for competitiveness and employment. Furthermore, studies are now under way into VET's economic and social benefits (New skills agenda for Europe, 2016).

In this context, this paper addresses the new sources of productivity available to Spanish industry, particularly against the background of analysis of the effects of knowledge spillover, as viewed from the perspective of the role played by employees' vocational training. The paper studies the business strategies of Spanish companies according to the qualification of the workers in terms of vocational education and training. First, it aims to identify and study the general characteristics of Spanish manufacturing companies and their differences based on human resources employed with professional training. Second, the aim is to analyse the differences in productivity, innovation and competitiveness of companies that have a higher proportion of personnel with professional training.

This analysis is part of a collaborative research project between the SEPI Foundation and the Bankia Foundation for Dual Training to gather information in relation to the professional training of workers in the manufacturing sector.

2 Methodology

This analysis is developed quantitatively, through econometric techniques, within the framework of the Business Strategies Survey, which is an annual panel survey, aimed at industrial manufacturing companies based in Spain.

This survey has been in operation since 1990 between the Ministry of Industry and the SEPI Foundation, having an annual average of 1800 industrial companies been surveyed using a questionnaire with 107 questions and more than 500 specific fields, and which also includes information on the firms' balance sheet together with their profit and loss statements. The SEPI Foundation preserves the consistency and quality of the time series and produces the corresponding 'Annual Report and Statistical Tables'. The ESEE's population of reference is composed of firms with 10 or more employees within the manufacturing industry. The geographical scope of reference is the Spanish economy, and the survey uses yearly variables. One of the most relevant characteristics of the ESEE is its representativeness. The initial selection was carried out combining exhaustiveness and random sampling criteria. Those firms with more than 200 employees were included in the first category. The second category was composed by firms employing 10-to-200 workers. These firms were selected through a stratified, proportional and systematic sampling with a random seed (SEPI, 2018). The ESEE is oriented towards capturing information about firms' strategies including information about (1) 'activity, products and manufacturing processes,' (2) 'customers and suppliers', (3) 'costs and prices', (4) 'markets, (5) 'technological activities', (6) 'foreign trade'', (7) 'accounting

data' and (8) 'employment' The last variable includes the number of employees working in the firm, its structure according to the type of contracts, their professional categories and qualifications, as well as other information needed to calculate the effective work-time during the year.

The survey referred to 2016-2017 incorporates, for the first time, some items related to VET, as a result of this piece of collaborative research between both foundations. The design of the 'Vet' items was elaborated for both foundations and the survey and statistical treatment was done by Sepi Foundation (Díaz-Chao and Torrent-Sellens, 2018). The analysis of the data is developed from a knowledge economy approach, allowing a better understanding of business strategies according to similarities and differences in VET keys; in terms of business characteristics and productivity, innovation, etc.

The contribution of this research makes to the field lies in its novel comparative approach and in the quantitative scale of the sample. Nevertheless, we are aware that the research has its limitations and that it is necessary to continue study in this significant scientific

3 Results and discussion

3.1 From a descriptive analysis

Firstly, one fifth of employees working in Spanish industry have VET qualifications. In total, 21.9% of staff employed in Spanish industry hold a VET qualification and 14.5% have a university qualification. The remaining 63.6% have either a school-leaving certificate (ISCED 2) or no qualifications at all. In short, most of Spanish industry's employees do not hold any qualifications, a situation that is accentuated in industrial SMEs (firms with 200 employees or fewer), where the figure stands at 66.6%. Therefore, it seems to be that training remains a challenge that industry has yet to address, as evidenced by the fact that around two thirds of people working in industry have no qualifications at all. Meanwhile, around one fifth of them have a vocational qualification and a further 15% are university graduates.

Secondly, in industrial SMEs most workers (66.6%) do not hold a qualification. The breakdown by level of education also reveals that 20.4% of employees hold vocational qualifications and 13.1% hold higher qualifications. For their part, in large enterprises (with over 200 employees) the breakdown reveals higher levels of education and training, although the number of staff without any qualifications remains significant (49.5%). In large industrial enterprises the proportions of employees with vocational or university qualifications stand at 29.5% and 21.0%, respectively. So far, as companies grow, so the number of employees with vocational or university qualifications likewise increases.

Thirdly, the data compiled also highlight that, when measured by percentage of companies, the breakdown of firms' human capital is clearly unequal. In around half of Spain's industrial companies, employees with vocational qualifications make up just 14.5% of the workforce. In contrast, in the 10% of firms at the upper end of the scale, the proportion of VET graduates rises to 58%. Similarly, in around half of Spain's industrial companies' university graduates account for merely 11% of the workforce. Conversely, in the 10% of firms at the upper end of the scale, the proportion of university graduates stands at 32.7%.

3.2 From the employment and human resource perspective

Firstly, it should be noted that vocational qualifications are associated with greater job stability. The proportion of salaried staff on permanent, full-time contracts is higher in companies that employ people with vocational qualifications (83.7% of the total).

Secondly, in addition to this greater job stability, VET is also associated with greater efforts to train employees. In firms that employ VET graduates, both internal expenditure per

employee (€1.40) and external expenditure per employee (€106.60) are clearly higher than in companies without workers with vocational qualifications.

Finally, the greater stability and emphasis on training in companies with staff with vocational qualifications also translates into higher salaries. Thus, in 2016, the average personnel cost per employee in these companies was just over €44,500, a figure 28.7% higher than among firms that did not employ VET graduates.

3.3 From the technology and innovation perspective

One of the first things to highlight about companies that employ staff with vocational qualifications is their greater propensity to invest in R&D. In total, 30.2% of industrial firms carry out and/or subcontract R&D. The data on R&D expenditure as a percentage of sales reveal a similar trend. For those companies that employ VET graduates, the ratio stands at 0.84%. The higher technology intensity among firms that employ personnel with vocational qualifications is clearly linked to their greater capacity to develop collaborative networks: 13.6% partner with VET centres, 17.1% with suppliers and 20.4% with universities and research centres. In addition, they also stand out for their greater capacity to evaluate technological change (20.1%) and to recruit staff with corporate R&D experience (6.3%).

The findings for R&D are replicated for innovation. In other words, innovation intensity is greater among firms that employ staff with vocational qualifications. It is worth highlighting here that nearly one in five (19.8%) industrial firms in Spain has an innovation plan in place. Another thing that distinguishes industrial companies that employ people with vocational qualifications is that they work on innovation in a variety of fields: product innovation (13.6%), process innovation (33.9%), organisational innovation (18.7%) and sales and marketing innovation (16.0%).

By implementing a value-generation process that makes more intensive use of human capital, technology, R&D and innovation, industrial firms that employ VET graduates could also be expected to perform better. The data obtained confirm that premise. Firstly, industrial firms with staff with vocational qualifications generate higher sales volumes (€3.5 million), create more gross value added (€13.9 million) and have more assets (€6.3 million) and employees (177.8 on average) than companies that do not employ people with vocational qualifications.

3.4 From the efficiency perspective

A second key finding is that industrial firms that employ personnel with vocational qualifications are clearly more efficient than those that do not. This becomes evident when analysing productivity figures per employee and per hour worked. While productivity among industrial companies that employ people with vocational qualifications stands at €3,500 per employee and at €36.30 per hour worked, among firms that do not employ VET graduates it is significantly lower (€2,600 per employee and €24.20 per hour worked).

4 Conclusions

These data reveal that VET has clear positive effects on the value that industrial firms generate through innovation and development of human capital, as well as boosting staff salaries and increasing business efficiency.

The contribution of this research makes to the field lies in its novel comparative approach and in the quantitative scale of the sample. Nevertheless, we are aware that the research has its limitations and that it is necessary to continue study in this significant scientific field.

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Biographical notes

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